

Flying Intelligent Surfaces: Joint Adjustment of Position and Configuration for UAV-Mounted RIS

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Abstract—Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS) are a technology expected to meet the demanding objectives of future wireless networks by manipulating and reflecting electromagnetic waves using real-time adjustable elements to improve communication performance. However, due to multiplicative path loss, RIS are most effective when used in line-of-sight and proximity to the transmitter or receiver. Moreover, as mobility is a common feature in wireless communication networks, guaranteeing these requirements can be challenging — unless the RIS has the ability to reposition itself.

To investigate the efficacy of RIS for improving communication quality in such networks, we mounted a RIS prototype on an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV). By conducting experimental measurements and recording the UAV-mounted RIS trajectory during its flights, the measured data was reconstructed through numerical simulations to extract the key factors. To further bridge simulations and measurements, we extract the gain characterizing the improvement in communication performance resulting from real-time adjustments of the RIS configuration, compared to a fixed configuration. Numerical evaluations indicate that a real-time adjusted RIS may result in a gain of up to 20dB.

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS) is envisioned to be one of the prime candidate technologies that enable the demanding objectives for future sixth-generation (6G) of wireless communication networks [1]. Incorporating RIS in wireless networks makes it possible to regulate the characteristics of the propagation environment. This is enabled by the control of the wavefront, e.g., the phase, amplitude, and frequency, of the impinging signal [1, 2]. This distinctive characteristic makes the RIS-assisted network not only an enabling platform for a variety of novel applications in the physical layer [3, 4], but can also boost various communication objectives, such as the capacity, resilience, and energy efficiency [1–3, 5, 6]. To this end, the RIS has to be specifically configured to support the desired use case. In addition to the chosen configuration, the RIS’s deployment position also plays a major role, due to the multiplicative path loss caused by the

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links from the transmitter (Tx) to the RIS and from the RIS to the receiver (Rx). As a consequence, the contribution of the RIS to the communication network becomes most effective when deployed in line-of-sight (LoS) towards both, Tx and Rx. Furthermore, it has been shown that deploying the RIS in proximity to the Tx or Rx also has a significant influence on the resulting performance [7]. However, satisfying these requirements in wireless communication systems, especially with mobile users and blockages, cannot be ensured.

Consequently, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) are being proposed to relocate the RIS, such that an LoS-link can be guaranteed despite user mobility [8, 9]. Compared to a base station (BS), the low weight and power efficiency of RIS make it a suitable option for attachment to UAVs, significantly extending their flight time. From a theoretical perspective, mounting the RIS to the UAV not only opens up more degrees of freedom but also couples the position to the optimal RIS configuration. More precisely, since the configuration of the RIS is dependent on its relative position with respect to the Tx and Rx, the RIS can be optimally configured while the UAV is repositioning as well. However, by considering practical limitations, i.e., one-bit quantized phase shifts of the RIS elements, the beamsteering at the RIS becomes quantized as well. Hence, choosing a position or trajectory that considers these limitations becomes an equally important task.

To the best of our knowledge, this paper is the first to validate the feasibility of a RIS-mounted UAV in the context of wireless communications, supported by prototypical validation. Accordingly, our objective is to extract significant insights from the measurements to reconcile any disparities between theoretical models and experimental observations.

II. SYSTEM AND CHANNEL MODEL

We assume a scenario, where the communication of two devices has been impeded by a mobile blockage [3]. As a countermeasure, the UAV-mounted RIS is dispatched to aid in restoring the blocked communication link by providing the RIS-reflected communication link. We replicate this scenario, by considering the experimental setup depicted in Fig. 1 (left) and assume a single-antenna Tx and Rx with main axis intersection at a reference point ρ_{ref} as depicted in Fig. 2. The RIS prototype is a rectangular array of M controllable reflecting elements, allowing for configurable phase shifts in

Figure 1. The figure on the left shows the utilized antenna setup with the receive antenna tilted 45° towards the transmit antenna. On the right the RIS prototype can be seen mounted to a customized Holybro X500 next to a Hex Herelink 1.1 controller.

the reflection and resulting in the effective Tx-RIS-Rx channel $h^{\text{eff}} = \sum_{m=1}^M h_m \theta_m g_m$, where h_m (g_m) denotes the channel coefficient between the Tx (Rx) and the m -th RIS element. The phase shift, induced on the reflection by the m -th RIS element, is denoted by $\theta_m = A_m(\varphi_m) e^{j\varphi_m}$, where φ_m is the adjustable phase and $A_m \in [0, 1]$ the phase-dependent reflect amplitude. As the experiments are conducted in a UAV laboratory environment, multipath effects between the Tx-Rx link as well as additional noise from the UAV can be expected. However, to validate the feasibility under the given practical limitations, we model h_m and g_m using the free-space path loss (FSPL) formula [10]. In fact, based on previous measurements in an office environment [11], the theoretically-obtained RIS configurations using this channel model were still able to outperform experimentally-obtained ones. Thus, according to [10], we model the FSPL between Tx-RIS-Rx over the m -th RIS element as

$$h_m g_m \theta_m = \left[\frac{c}{4\pi f d_m^h} e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} d_m^h} \right] \left[\frac{c}{4\pi f d_m^g} e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} d_m^g} \right] \theta_m, \quad (1)$$

where c is the speed of light, f is the frequency and λ is the wavelength of the signal. In addition, d_m^h (d_m^g) denotes the distance between the Tx (Rx) and the m -th RIS element.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

A. Experimental Setup

To test the feasibility of the utilized channel model and highlight the dependence of the RIS configuration on the reference point, we set up a scenario utilizing a RIS prototype in the 5GHz band. The utilized UAV-mounted RIS prototype is shown in Fig. 1 and is described in greater detail in [12]. The $M = 64$ elements are laid out in an 8×8 grid sized 20×16 cm, where each element features a PIN diode to achieve the phase shifting. The surface is designed as a binary-switching surface with a 180° phase shift at the designed carrier frequency of 5.385GHz. To validate the performance of the current position, we use a vector network analyzer (VNA) of type PicoVNA 106 from manufacturer PicoTech. The S21 parameter is evaluated over a span of 800MHz, from 5.0GHz to 5.8GHz. Each of the two ports of the VNA is connected to a directional horn antenna of type LB-187-15-C-SF from manufacturer A-Info. The gain of the antennas within the chosen span is at least

16.35dBi. Both antennas were set up 0.62m apart from each other facing upwards, while the receiver is tilted 45° towards the transmitter as shown in Fig. 1. The antennas and the RIS are vertically polarized and correctly aligned during all flights.

The UAV carrying the RIS is a customized Holybro X500 Quadrotor equipped with a Pixhawk Cube Orange flight controller. Since the UAV was originally designed for outdoor applications with GPS information as position feedback, the open-source autopilot software system Ardupilot¹, mostly used for GPS-based outdoor flights, is running on the Pixhawk controller. We replaced the position information received from the GPS antenna with position measurements performed by a Motion Capture System (MCS) to enable indoor autonomous flights. As MCS, 10 Vicon Vantage V5 infrared cameras and the software Tracker 3 were installed, able to track objects equipped with an asymmetric pattern of reflective markers with a precision of more than 1 mm². The MCS is used to measure the position of the UAV including the RIS and the components of the Tx-Rx-setup. The position measurement of the UAV not only serves as an input to the Extended Kalman filter (EKF) running on the Cube Orange flight controller estimating the position and orientation of the UAV but is also recorded for evaluation purposes. We use an ESP8266 Microcontroller and the MAVESP8266 firmware³ to send the position information via an additional WiFi connection to the UAV during flight time. The position information is converted to GPS data before transmission using the MAVProxy⁴ software and the associated Vicon module. All necessary steps to replace the GPS position information with the MCS are described in the Ardupilot documentation⁵. The communication to the UAV is established via a Hex Herelink 1.1 controller using a 2.4 GHz ISM band. The Herelink controller is used to transmit desired set points for the UAV position. The position information of the MCS sent to the UAV is used in a feedback controller to follow the transmitted set points. With a payload of up to 1kg, the RIS and all the necessary power infrastructure have been mounted using 3D-printed custom mounts as shown in Fig. 1. In order to keep the delays between measurements low, a USB cable is used for controlling the RIS configurations.

B. Analytical Optimization of the Surface State

Based on the previously defined channel model, we determine the optimal RIS configuration of a predefined reference position ρ_{ref} using the resulting geometry [11]. More precisely, we calculate the optimal RIS configuration analytically, i.e., $\varphi_m^*(C) = C - \varphi'_m$, where C is an arbitrary value for the desired phase at the receiver because there is no direct Tx-Rx link and $\varphi'_m = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}(d_m^h + d_m^g)$. As C can be chosen freely, we sweep over 360 equally-spaced phase values C , round the

¹<https://ardupilot.org/>

²https://www.vicon.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/PS4933_Standard-Individual-Case-Study_16_Vicon-Dynamic-Object-Tracking-Accuracy.pdf

³<https://github.com/dogmaphobic/mavesp8266>

⁴<https://ardupilot.org/mavproxy>

⁵<https://ardupilot.org/copter/docs/common-vicon-for-nongps-navigation.html>

continuous phase values to the nearest switching state of the RIS prototype, and compare the simulated performances of the resulting RIS-provided links. The equivalent mathematical representation can be written as

$$C^{\text{opt}} = \underset{C}{\operatorname{argmax}} \left| \sum_{m=1}^M h_m g_m A_m(\operatorname{rd}(\varphi_m^*(C))) e^{j\operatorname{rd}(\varphi_m^*(C))} \right|, \quad (2)$$

$$\text{s.t. } A_m(\tau) = \begin{cases} -2\text{dB}, & \text{if } \tau = \pi \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (3)$$

$$\operatorname{rd}(\tau) = \begin{cases} \pi, & \text{if } \frac{\pi}{2} \leq \tau < \frac{3\pi}{2} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

where we assume an additional attenuation of 2dB to the reflected path of reflecting element m if it is turned on, capturing the hardware limitations of the utilized RIS prototype. After obtaining the optimal phase values C^{opt} from (2), the optimal configuration $\varphi_{\text{ref},m}^* = \operatorname{rd}(\varphi_m^*(C^{\text{opt}}))$ for the reference point ρ_{ref} can be determined.

C. Experimental Results

In this subsection, we distinguish two experimental measurements from one another: The *hand-guided* scenario, in which the UAV-mounted RIS is carried by hand, while the UAV is turned off, to simulate autonomous movement, and the *remote-controlled* scenario, in which desired set points are given to the UAV with a remote control by a human pilot. As illustrated in Fig. 2, the starting position of the UAV-mounted RIS is chosen in such a way that the trajectory of the UAV first passes over the receiving antenna, then through the reference point φ_{ref}^* . The figure also shows that φ_{ref}^* was chosen slightly offset from the transmitting antenna so that the UAV would be able to land beside both antennas at any time. In both depicted scenarios, the RIS alternatively changes its state from turning all elements off (OFF-state) to the determined optimal configuration φ_{ref}^* (OPT-state) at the reference point ρ_{ref} . Since this version of the RIS prototype does not confirm the completion of its reconfiguration, guard intervals are used in order to ensure that the RIS has successfully changed its configuration before the measurements are taken. Hence, each measurement requires approximately 0.335s to adjust all elements at the RIS and take the S21 measurement with the VNA, using the 'logmag' command within the VNA software.

Additionally, Fig. 2 illustrates the recorded trajectories of the hand-guided (left) and remote-controlled (right) UAV-mounted RIS. Specifically, the recorded positions correspond to the center of the RIS prototype. These figures also show the exact positions and their associated RIS configuration at the time of taking the measurements, denoted by red circles for the OPT-state and blue circles for the OFF-state. As the RIS state is changing alternatively between these two states, the measurements (circles) taken on the trajectories are also alternating along the trajectories. When comparing the hand-guided trajectory in Fig. 2 on the left with the remote-controlled one on the right, it becomes evident that the movement speed of the RIS in the hand-guided case was much slower and more steady. This can be concluded by the higher

Figure 2. System setup and trajectory of the **hand-guided** (left) and **remote-controlled** (right) UAV-mounted RIS.

Figure 3. S21 magnitudes and their means $\overline{S21}$ of the measurements with the OFF-state and OPT-state for the **hand-guided** case as well as the distances towards the reference point ρ_{ref} .

density of measurement points and much straighter trajectory. The trajectory disturbances shown in Fig. 2 (right) are mainly caused by the USB cable used to connect the RIS, which interfered with the UAV's position controller. Additionally, it should be noted that the remote-controlled trajectory runs twice over both antennas to counteract the loss in precision due to the increased flight speed of the UAV.

Corresponding to the circles along the trajectories in Fig. 2, Figs. 3 and 4 illustrate the S21 parameters and their means $\overline{S21}$ over the observed interval for the hand-guided and remote-controlled case, respectively. The figures also specify the distance d_{ref} to the reference point for each measured position along the respective trajectory. Fig. 3 shows that when the RIS is positioned close to the reference point ρ_{ref} , the quality of the communication link increases for both, the OPT-state and OFF-state. This is expected due to the directivity of the horn antennas and their orientation towards ρ_{ref} . In this regime, the OPT-state generally outperforms the OFF-state with a mean performance advantage of 2.44dB, while an increase in performance of up to 12dB is observed at specific points. For the remote-controlled case depicted in Fig. 4, the two traversals through the reference point ρ_{ref} are clearly illustrated by the two pronounced minima of the orange curves. Similarly to the hand-guided case, the OPT-state outperforms the OFF-state with a mean performance advantage of 1.09dB and by up to 10dB at certain points. Consequently, the beneficial effects of providing the optimal RIS state depending on the position is

Figure 4. S21 magnitudes and their means $\overline{S21}$ of the measurements with the OFF-state and OPT-state for the **remote-controlled** case as well as the distances towards the reference point ρ_{ref} .

evident in spite of the disturbances caused by repositioning the RIS with the UAV.

IV. THEORETICAL LIMITS BASED ON MEASUREMENTS

A. Constructive Interference Factor (CIF)

This section compares the experimentally obtained S21 parameters discussed in Section III to their theoretically achievable counterparts. The theoretical S21 parameters are calculated using the UAV position data recorded by the MCS at a frequency of 100Hz. Hence, the simulation provides an estimate of what the S21 parameters would have been if the VNA measurements were taken at the same frequency instead of roughly 3Hz. For the simulations, we consider two RIS strategies: The first one is utilizing the fixed configuration φ_{ref}^* for the reference point ρ_{ref} for the whole trajectory. This essentially results in a simulative reconstruction of the experimental measurements with the OPT-state that are depicted by the red curves in Fig. 3 and 4. For the second RIS strategy, we assume that the RIS and the MCS are operating optimally within a closed-loop system. As a result, the RIS is reconfigurable at 100Hz, i.e., with the optimal configuration using (2) at every recorded position with the MCS.

As the phase shifts at the RIS are subject to the quantization caused by (4), we introduce the concept of a constructive interference factor (CIF). The CIF quantifies the degree to which the waves reflected by the RIS interact constructively at the receiver and thus characterizes the impact of the quantization on the RIS-provided communication link. Mathematically, the CIF can be expressed by substituting (1) and the definition of θ_m into h^{eff} resulting in

$$h^{eff} = \frac{c^2}{(4\pi f)^2} \sum_{m=1}^M \overbrace{\frac{A_m(\varphi_m)}{d_m^h d_m^g} e^{j\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}(d_m^h + d_m^g) + \varphi_m\right)}}^{CIF(\varphi)}. \quad (5)$$

Note that during the simulations, the distances d_m^h and d_m^g are given from the recorded position data. While the performance with fixed φ_{ref}^* depends on the distance d_{ref} to the reference point ρ_{ref} , the CIF depends on the mean of the distances of the RIS-provided paths $d_{eff} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M d_m^h d_m^g$.

Fig. 5 illustrates this dependency for the hand-guided scenario by depicting these distances (normalized) in addition to the according CIFs for the simulation of both, the fixed configuration $CIF(\varphi_{ref}^*)$ and the continuously optimized configurations $CIF(\varphi_{opt,t}^*)$ in each time instance t . The normalized distances are defined as $\tilde{d}_{ref} = d_{ref}(t)/\max_t(d_{ref}(t))$ and

Figure 5. CIF and relative distances of the fixed and continuously optimized RIS simulations along the **hand-guided** trajectory.

Figure 6. CIF and relative distances of the fixed and continuously optimized RIS simulations along the **remote-controlled** trajectory.

$\tilde{d}_{eff} = d_{eff}(t)/\max_t(d_{eff}(t))$, where the max-operator refers to the maximum $\forall t$ attained on the time interval of observation. It can be observed that the simulation with the fixed configuration $CIF(\varphi_{opt}^*)$ has the highest CIF when the distance to the reference point ρ_{ref} is the lowest. However, since the reference point ρ_{ref} is not being traversed precisely, the fixed RIS configuration φ_{ref}^* is not optimal at this position. Thus, comparing $CIF(\varphi_{ref}^*)$ to $CIF(\varphi_{opt,t}^*)$ at this position reveals that the optimal $\varphi_{opt,t}^*$ roughly doubles the CIF as compared to φ_{ref}^* . Interestingly, the curve for the $CIF(\varphi_{opt,t}^*)$ reaches its peak earlier in time, specifically when the RIS is positioned close to the two antennas. As the optimal configuration $\varphi_{opt,t}^*$ adjusts the RIS to counteract the distant-dependent phase changes caused by the exponential function in (5), the distance-dependent amplitude becomes the most impactful factor. Due to the fact, that the amplitude is inversely proportional to the distances d_m^h and d_m^g , the CIF for the continuously optimized RIS performs best when the overall RIS-provided link is the shortest. Additionally, the figure shows that even when the RIS is continuously adjusted, multiple local maxima can be observed. These are caused by the quantization of the RIS phase shifts in (4) and the increased attenuation that is introduced if a RIS element is turned on.

Fig. 6 shows the respective CIFs and distances as well as their correlation for the remote-controlled case. Here, it can be observed that the number of local maxima within the CIFs and the symmetry of the CIFs around their peaks differ greatly when compared to the hand-guided case. These differences are due to a less steady trajectory and higher velocity, which becomes evident by the density of the circles in Fig. 2 (right).

B. Interpolated Performance Gain for a Closed-Loop System

In this section, we explore the potential performance improvement that could be achieved by operating the MCS

Figure 7. $S21_{h^{\text{eff}}}$ magnitudes for the simulations with fixed and continuously adjusted RIS configurations of the **hand-guided** trajectory as well as the interpolated experimental $S21$ magnitude of continuously readjusting the RIS.

and RIS in a closed-loop system. To accomplish this, we compare the disparity between the CIF gain of the fixed and continuously optimized RIS configurations. Given the recorded trajectories, these gains become solely dependent on the RIS configurations. By applying these gain differences to the experimental measurements, we can interpolate the performance that a closed-loop system could have achieved. To this end, we express the effective channel h^{eff} in dB and decouple the CIF as

$$S21_{h^{\text{eff}}}(\varphi) = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{c^2}{(4\pi f)^2} \right) + 10 \log_{10}(|\text{CIF}(\varphi)|). \quad (6)$$

By calculating the ratio between $\text{CIF}(\varphi_{\text{opt},t}^*)$ and $\text{CIF}(\varphi_{\text{ref}}^*)$, we isolate the CIF gain that is purely dependent on the RIS configuration. Subsequently, the isolated CIF gain is added to the $S21$ measurements obtained by VNA ($S21_{\text{meas}}$) to infer the performance gain achieved by optimizing the RIS in-flight as

$$S21_{\text{interp}} = |S21_{\text{meas}}| + \left| 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{CIF}(\varphi_{\text{opt},t}^*)}{\text{CIF}(\varphi_{\text{ref}}^*)} \right) \right|. \quad (7)$$

Fig. 7 depicts the $S21$ magnitude for the fixed ($S21_{h^{\text{eff}}}(\varphi_{\text{ref}}^*)$) and continuously optimized ($S21_{h^{\text{eff}}}(\varphi_{\text{opt},t}^*)$) RIS configurations for both simulated and experimental settings for the hand-guided trajectory. Interestingly, when comparing the maxima of the $S21_{h^{\text{eff}}}(\varphi_{\text{ref}}^*)$ (black) and $S21_{\text{meas}}$ (red) curves at the time instances 224s, 226s and 227.5s, three distinct peaks can be observed for both curves. This indicates that the CIF is also observable in the experimental domain. The figure also illustrates the largest gain of up to 20dB between the experimentally measured and interpolated curves occurring at the maximum of the $\text{CIF}(\varphi_{\text{opt},t}^*)$ curve, which corresponds to the most favorable location on the trajectory. However as the configuration φ_{ref}^* displays a local minimum at this position, optimal reconfiguration of the RIS at this location results in a significant performance increase. Similarly, Fig. 8 depicts the $S21$ magnitudes of the simulations, measurements, and interpolations of the remote-controlled scenario. The figure shows reconfiguring the RIS along the trajectory would increase the $S21$ magnitude by about 10dB within the observed interval.

V. CONCLUSION

We experimentally demonstrated the feasibility of mounting and operating a RIS on a UAV. By pre-determining a theoretically optimal RIS configuration for a reference point before takeoff, we flew through this point while switching between the OFF and OPT states to collect two data sets for the

Figure 8. $S21_{h^{\text{eff}}}$ magnitudes for the simulations with fixed and continuously adjusted RIS configurations of the **remote-controlled** trajectory as well as the interpolated experimental $S21$ magnitude of continuously readjusting the RIS.

same trajectory. The results qualitatively validate the positive impact of adjusting the RIS configuration based on its position. To gain more insights, we reconstructed the experimental setup numerically using the recorded trajectories and proposed the constructive interference factor (CIF) to characterize the RIS-provided link. By simulating the setup with fixed and continuously adjusting phase shifts, we isolated the CIF gain dependent on the correct RIS configuration. Applying these gains to the experimental measurements, we inferred the expected practical performance of the UAV-mounted RIS reconfiguring in real time. Our evaluation shows potential gains of up to 20dB compared to initial measurements.

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REFERENCES

- [1] E. Basar, M. Di Renzo, J. De Rosny, M. Debbah, M.-S. Alouini, and R. Zhang, "Wireless communications through reconfigurable intelligent surfaces," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 116 753–116 773, 2019.
- [2] M. Jian, G. C. Alexandropoulos, E. Basar, C. Huang, R. Liu, Y. Liu, and C. Yuen, "Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces for wireless communications: Overview of hardware designs, channel models, and estimation techniques," *Intelli. and Conv. Netw.*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 1–32, 2022.
- [3] K. Weinberger, R.-J. Reifert, A. Sezgin, and E. Basar, "RIS-enhanced resilience in cell-free MIMO," *WSA&SCC*, 2023.
- [4] S. Tewes, M. Heinrichs, R. Kronberger, and A. Sezgin, "IRS-enabled breath tracking with colocated commodity WiFi transceivers," *IEEE IoT Journ.*, 2022.
- [5] K. Weinberger, A. A. Ahmad, and A. Sezgin, "On synergistic benefits of rate splitting in IRS-assisted cloud radio access networks," in *IEEE ICC*, 2021, pp. 1–6.
- [6] K. Weinberger, A. A. Ahmad, A. Sezgin, and A. Zappone, "Synergistic benefits in IRS- and RS-enabled C-RAN with energy-efficient clustering," *IEEE TWC*, vol. 21, no. 10, pp. 8459–8475, 2022.
- [7] E. Björnson, O. Özdogan, and E. G. Larsson, "Intelligent reflecting surface versus decode-and-forward: How large surfaces are needed to beat relaying?" *IEEE Wirel. Commun. Lett.*, 9(2), pp. 244–248, 2020.
- [8] S. Li, B. Duo, X. Yuan, Y.-C. Liang, and M. Di Renzo, "Reconfigurable intelligent surface assisted UAV communication: Joint trajectory design and passive beamforming," *IEEE Wirel. Commun. Lett.*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 716–720, 2020.
- [9] Y. Li, C. Yin, T. Do-Duy, A. Masaracchia, and T. Q. Duong, "Aerial reconfigurable intelligent surface-enabled URLLC UAV systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 140 248–140 257, 2021.
- [10] A. Goldsmith, *Wireless communications*. Cambridge Univ. Press, 2005.
- [11] K. Weinberger, S. Tewes, M. Heinrichs, R. Kronberger, and A. Sezgin, "RIS-based channel modeling and prototypical validation," *WSA*, 2023.
- [12] S. Tewes, M. Heinrichs, P. Staat, R. Kronberger, and A. Sezgin, "Full-duplex meets reconfigurable surfaces: RIS-assisted SIC for full-duplex radios," in *IEEE ICC*, 2022, pp. 1106–1111.